

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MOFOLO****FIRST NAME: ROSALIA****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 13%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MS Word - Office 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which structure of the essay should the academic paper follow?

- Introduction, body, and conclusion.**¹
- Draft, edit, and redraft.
- Topic sentence, supporting sentence, and analysis.
- Start writing early, have a plan, and check the spelling.

2. EUCLID advocates for ----- rules even though it accepts other styles.

- American Psychological Association.
- Chicago.**²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 10.

²Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 41.

- Oxford.
 - Havard.
3. The main difference between US and UK English lies in their-----?
- Population.
 - National histories.
 - Rise to global importance during World War II.
 - Spelling and punctuations.**³
4. Which two citation styles does Kate Turabian describe in the Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations?
- Title-bibliography style and notes-date style.
 - Notes-bibliography style and author-date style.**⁴
 - Title-bibliography style and author-title style.
 - Book-date style and author-time style.
5. When is a researcher allowed not to give credit to the author?
- When using in-text quotations.
 - When information can be accessed from several sources.**⁵
 - When using quotations.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 24 and 32.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 141.

⁵ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack*, 37.

- When using your own words as much as possible.
6. Which author describes the nature and characteristics of a successful dissertation in their book?
- James P. Sampson.**⁶
- Kate L. Turabian.
- Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe.
- Kabiru Gulma.
7. Which dissertation research component is the most comprehensive document?
- Dissertation prospectus.
- Dissertation manuscript.
- Dissertation concept paper.
- Dissertation.**⁷
8. Which of the following is not true about Zotero?
- Zotero uses Chrome web browser and Microsoft Word plug-in.
- Zotero automatically syncs to the cloud if this preference is enabled.
- Zotero automatically saves PDF details together with citations.**⁸

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 6.

⁷ Sampson, *Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 9.

⁸ Kabiru Gulma, "Editing & Cleaning Zotero Entries," February 1, 2022, YouTube video, 12:27 to 12:48, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nz8MJtEqbQk>.

- Zotero allows one to change the format or style of the paper.
9. What is the name of an international and intergovernmental organization comprising 27 countries?
- The European Union.**⁹
- The Council.
- The European Communities.
- Brexit.
10. Besides Zotero, which other two citation management tools do Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations cite?
- Grammarly.
- BibTex.
- Mendeley.
- EndNote and RefWorks.**¹⁰

⁹ European Union, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union, 2016), 71.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition, 145.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

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Gulma, Kabiru. "Editing & Cleaning Zotero Entries." February 1, 2022. YouTube video, 16:09, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nz8MJtEqbQk> (accessed November 5, 2023).

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second ed. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.